

A STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SELECTED TEXTILE INDUSTRIES BEFORE AND AFTER GST IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT:

In the past, the traditional method of taxation in India faced several issues. However, with the introduction of GST, the tax burden on customers has been reduced. GST encompasses all sectors of the Indian economy, including textiles, which is a major industry for employment in the country. The primary aim of this research is to assess the financial performance of the textile industry post-GST implementation in India. The study examines the relationship between the annual growth rate and various financial performance metrics of the Indian textile sector over a twelve-year period from 2012 to 2023. Secondary data from profit and loss accounts of selected companies were gathered from databases such as Money Control and Economic Times. The study utilizes tools such as Annual Growth Rate (AGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) to measure the financial performance of five selected textile industries in India. The findings indicate that the growth rate in the textile sector following the implementation of GST had a positive impact on the financial performance of these selected industries.

Keywords: Taxation, GST, Textile Industry, Financial performance, AGR, AAGR, CAGR.

INTRODUCTION:

GST is a comprehensive indirect and value-added tax imposed by both the State and Central Governments on goods and services sold within the country. It represents a unified tax structure covering all stages of supply chain, from manufacturers to end consumers. Goods and services are categorized into five tax slabs for the collection of indirect taxes: 0%, 5%, 12%, 18%, and 28%. The Indian textile industry predominantly relies on manufacturing and exporting textile products, playing a crucial role in the national economy. It constitutes nearly 14% of the total industrial production and contributes around 3% to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country. This industry is a significant driver of employment, providing opportunities for over 35 million people. In developed countries, the production output of woven products remains consistently robust. The weaving process is essential for creating fabrics used across a wide spectrum of clothing types.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The textile industry plays a critical role in providing essential employment opportunities and fostering sustained economic growth to enhance living standards. Positioned as a self-reliant sector, it manages the entire value chain from raw material production to delivering finished goods, adding significant value at each stage. It is a cornerstone of the country's economic advancement. However, since the implementation of GST, textile industries have encountered numerous challenges. These include issues such as working capital shortages, raw material scarcity, technical challenges, labor shortages, problems with input tax credit, high production costs, low profitability, and managerial inefficiencies. These factors collectively hinder the financial growth of the industries. Overall financial performance is a crucial indicator that reflects an industry's growth trajectory, trend values, and operational efficiency. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the financial performance and determine whether the selected five textile industries have experienced positive or negative growth post-GST implementation.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

- To assess the financial status of five selected textile industries from 2012 to 2023.
- To calculate the Annual Growth Rate (AGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the specified period.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study relies on secondary data sourced from diverse sources including research journals, reports from databases like Money Control and Economic Times, and Annual Reports of selected textile industries in India. To ensure comprehensive data coverage and reliability, additional information from various publications, books, journals, and relevant websites pertaining to the textile industry has also been utilized.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY:

The study examines data spanning ten financial years from 2012-2013 to 2022-2023.

SAMPLING:

The study focuses on the top five textile industries in India, namely:

1)Arvind Ltd, 2)Vardhman Ltd, 3)Welspun India Ltd. 4)Raymond Ltd and 5)Trident Ltd

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS:

The financial performance of the selected five textile industries was analyzed using Annual Growth Rate (AGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR).

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

- The study restricted to selected textile companies only.
- Period of study was twelve years only.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:❖ **ARVIND LTD.:****TABLE 1
GROWTH RATE FOR ARVIND LTD**

DETAILS	YEARS											
	BASE	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
OPERATING REVENUE	3494.12	3780.29	4775.48	5224.69	5407.26	5980.96	6420.42	6435.96	6705.31	4528.54	7459.57	7722.69
AGR	-	8%	26%	9%	3%	11%	7%	0%	4%	-32%	65%	4%
AAGR	10%											
CAGR	7%											

Sources: www.moneycontrol.com/fiancials

The table illustrates the Annual Growth Rate (AGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for Arvind Ltd. from 2012-13 to 2022-2023. The AGR peaked at 65% in 2021-22 and reached its lowest point at 0% in 2018-2019. The Average Annual Growth Rate over the period is 10%, while the Compound Annual Growth Rate is 7%.

❖ **VARDHMAN LTD.:****TABLE 2
GROWTH RATE FOR VARDHMAN LTD**

DETAILS	YEARS											
	BASE	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
OPERATING REVENUE	3918	4159.74	5171.31	5742.03	5613.42	5690.43	5851.27	6414.58	6325.15	5787.64	9386.1	9840.79
AGR	-	6%	24%	11%	-2%	1%	3%	10%	-1%	-8%	62%	5%
AAGR	10%											
CAGR	9%											

Sources: www.moneycontrol.com/fiancials

The table shows the Annual Growth Rate (AGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for Vardhman Ltd. from 2012-13 to 2022-23. The AGR rose to 62% in 2021-22 and was lowest at -8% in 2020-2021. The

Average Annual Growth Rate remains steady at 10%, while the Compound Annual Growth Rate stands at 9%.

❖ WELSPUN INDIA LTD:

TABLE 3
GROWTH RATE FOR WELSPUN INDIA LTD

DETAILS	YEARS											
	BASE	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
OPERATING REVENUE	2590.49	3042.95	3531.2	4407.56	4885.01	5639.34	4976.6	5395.26	5323.57	5956.35	6703.47	5654.62
AGR	-	17%	16%	25%	11%	15%	-12%	8%	-1%	12%	13%	-16%
AAGR	8%											
CAGR	7%											

Sources:www.moneycontrol.com/fiancials

The table displays the Annual Growth Rate (AGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for Welspun Ltd. from 2012-13 to 2021-22. The AGR peaked at 25% in 2014-15 and reached its lowest point at -16% in 2022-2023. The Average Annual Growth Rate is 8%, while the Compound Annual Growth Rate stands at 7%.

❖ RAYMOND LTD:

TABLE 4
GROWTH RATE FOR RAYMOND LTD

DETAILS	YEARS											
	BASE	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
OPERATING REVENUE	1871.87	2032.39	2185.59	2645.32	2793.6	2822.18	3011.56	3276.39	3186.39	1752.41	4260.66	5779.56
AGR	-	9%	8%	21%	6%	1%	7%	9%	-3%	-45%	143%	36%
AAGR	17%											
CAGR	11%											

Sources:www.moneycontrol.com/fiancials

The table illustrates the Annual Growth Rate (AGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for Raymond Ltd. from 2012-13 to 2021-22. The AGR reached its peak at 143% in 2021-22 and its lowest point at -45% in 2020-2021. The Average Annual Growth Rate over the period is 17%, while the Compound Annual Growth Rate is 11%.

❖ **TRIDENT LTD:**

TABLE 5
GROWTH RATE FOR TRIDENT LTD

DETAILS	YEARS											
	BASE	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023
OPERATING REVENUE	2732	3335	3869	3754	3683	4617	4566	5220	4699	4519	6919	6267
AGR	-	22%	16%	-3%	-2%	25%	-1%	14%	-10%	-4%	53%	-9%
AAGR	9%											
CAGR	8%											

Sources: www.moneycontrol.com/fiancials

The analysis revealed the Annual Growth Rate (AGR), Average Annual Growth Rate (AAGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for Trident Ltd. from 2012-13 to 2021-22. The AGR peaked at 53% in 2021-22 and reached its lowest point at -10% in 2019-2020. The Average Annual Growth Rate for the period is 9%, while the Compound Annual Growth Rate stands at 8%.

FINDINGS, SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION:

The study found that, after GST implementation in selected five Textile industries in India had a positive growth rate. Highest annual growth rate obtain in Raymond Ltd is 143%, lowest annual growth rate obtain in Welspun India Ltd is 25%. The highest Compound annual growth rate obtain in Welspun India Ltd and Trident Ltd is 10%, lowest Compound annual growth rate obtain in Arvind Ltd is 8%. The study provides useful knowledge to the researchers and managers regarding annual growth rate and its relation with financial performance.

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